

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON ALKALI ACTIVATED CONCRETE CONTAINING FA AND GGBS WITH 20 % CEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In order to address environmental effects associated with two environmental situations are of concern, firstly the production of 1 ton of cement directly contributes 1 ton of carbon dioxide to the atmosphere, secondary is fly ash the waste product from coal based thermal power plants and Ground granulated blast furnace slag which is the last residue in the manufacture of iron. For both these material disposal is a serious concern as the agricultural lands are becoming draw back. An effort in this regard is the development of concrete, synthesized from the materials of geological origin or by product material such as fly ash and Ground granulated blast furnace slag which are rich in silicon, aluminum, ferrous oxide, calcium oxide magnesium oxide in certain percentages which develop the cementitious property when used as cement replacement material. The experiments were conducted on the development of an alkali-activated concrete by varying the concentration of NaOH and curing in ambient temperature. Alkali activated concrete containing materials such as, Fly ash, Ground granulated blast furnace slag and cement is prepared with designed proportion of 1:1.05:2.40 which is having 40% FA, 40% GGBS and 20% cement mixed with the various parameters such as alkali activator fluid consisting of sodium silicate and sodium hydroxide of different concentrations as 8M, 10M and 12M which is mixed one day prior. Activator solution to FA+GGBS+OPC ratio is kept constant as 0.35. By varying the ratio NaOH / Na₂SiO₃ i.e., 0.40 & 2.50 and Super plasticizers is used as carol indicator based naphthalene indicator as 1% to 2% Curing is done in ambient temperature and duration of curing on the compressive strength of concrete at different ages of 7, 14, 28, days has been incorporated and split tensile strength, flexural strength is done after 28 days. In the present investigation, a total number of 54 cube specimens of size 150 mm x150 mm x150 mm, for alkali-activated concrete and 9 cubes for conventional concrete are manufacture for testing compressive strength after the specimens cured 7,14,28 days in ambient temperature. 18 cylinders specimens of size 100 mm diameter and 200mm height for AAC and 3 cylinder for CVC are manufacture for testing of split tensile strength after the specimens cured 28 days in ambient temperature. 18 Prism specimens of size 100 mmx100mmx500mm for AAC and 3 prism for CVC are manufacture for testing of flexural strength after the specimens cured 28 days in ambient temperature. 14 beams of size 700mmx150mm x 150 mm, two beams each for Alkali-Activated reinforced concrete for mix A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, and two beams for conventional reinforced concrete for mix M30 are cast. The Flexural behaviour of the beam are observed by loading @ two point in one third span, first crack load, ultimate load and crack patterns are recorded. From the study it is found that the Alkali-Activation concrete of mix proportion “A3” i.e. 12M of NaOH & 0.4 ratio of (Na₂SiO₃/NaOH) containing 40% FA 40% GGBS & 20% ordinary Portland cement (OPC) shows good results when tested. Also The ultimate load carrying capacity of under reinforced beam of “A3” mix is 165KN and the deflection is 2.70mm which is about 28.26% less load carrying capacity of CVC beam of same dimension.

INDEX TERMS— Alkali activated concrete, alkaline solution